

PREDICTION OF BEST TYPE OF BRIDGE FOUNDATION USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUE

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Abstract : Soil- structure interaction is the challenging domine, as soil is heterogeneous in nature and structural component is homogeneous in nature. For selection of type of foundation to any particular structure in good old method we have to do soil investigation. As soil investigation is a time consuming process to bridge the time logging through this research article we articulated a procedure where in we stakeholder give input data in the form of questions, our designed Artificial Intelligence Technique supported GCLISP program based on the answers to questions it perform the best possible solution and gives the output as best foundation to that soil as well as that structural loading conditions.

Index Terms - Artificial Intelligence Technique, GCLISP, Input questions

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the study of how to make computers do things that, at the moment, people do better. AI is a field of study that encompasses computational techniques for performing tasks that apparently require intelligence when performed by humans. Such problems include diagnosing problems in engineering, designing new computers, writing stories and symphonies, finding mathematical theorems, assembling and inspecting products in factories and negotiating international treaties. It is a technology of information processing concerned with process reasoning, Learning and perception. Fundamental issues of AI involve knowledge representation, search, perception and inference. Knowledge may be available in many forms collections of logical assertions, heuristic rules, procedures, statistical correlations, etc. much of AI is concerned with the design and understanding of knowledge representation schemes. An understanding of search techniques can help us to avoid the combinatorial explosions that swamp the brute force attempts. Inference is the process of creating explicit representation of knowledge from implicit ones.

It is essential that before structure analysis and design, the type of bridge foundation is to be selected for a proposed site. The choice of the type of bridge foundation best suited to a particular location is a matter on which experienced engineers defer considerably. It is quite often, purely a matter of Judgment and experience. Unless a designer has enough experience and a wealth of knowledge, it is not an easy task for him/her to select the most suitable type of bridge foundation for the given site. The selection of the type of bridge foundation at a proposed site depends upon many physical factors such as topography, geological conditions, availability of materials and funds, data about earthquake, etc. Before selecting the best type of bridge foundation for a particular site one must consider the characteristics of each type of bridge foundation as related to the physical features of the site and the functions of the bridge foundation is supposed to serve, as well as economy, safety and other pertinent limitations. The choice of a bridge foundation may also be guided by many local problems such as availability of labor and equipment, accessibility of site, as well as time required for its construction.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Thomas (1993) and Guy(1993) Says that The five areas of active research are (a) intelligent aids for mechanical engineering design, (b) active experimentation as a method in machine learning, (c) techniques for combining logic programming and assumption-based truth maintenance, (d) methods for combining symbolic and numeric approaches to reasoning under uncertainty, and (e) problem-solving strategies for working with multiple qualitative **Models and Guy (1993)** says Lisp in one of the programming language to support te above criteria. **Choi (1993)** says that This paper details the expert system SUPERX used to select the super-structure type of bridges based on experience and knowledge of the domain experts. **Rich (1992)** says that system is made up of a working memory is initialized after the declarations and rules have been loaded. The knowledge base comprises of the knowledge unit for the generation of the candidates and the knowledge unit for the evaluation of the generated candidates, similar observations was made by **Winston (1984), Rajasekran (1993), Miles and moore (1991) and salata (1991)**. The database is used during the evaluation of each candidate and it was stored in the 16 separate data files. In his experimental study SUPERX is implemented with the expert system tool which uses the production system for knowledge representation and provides the mechanism of forward chaining.

3. METHODOLOGY

In our research work we used GCLISP is in acronym for golden common LISt processing. John McCarthy and his group developed the programming language LISP at the Massachusetts institute of technology in the late 1950's by John McCarthy and his group. GCLISP is a symbolic processing language. One of its main features that made it an extremely attractive language for AI is its use of list as a data structure. A list in GCLISP is a sequence of elements; each element may either be an atom or another list. The term atom means a single object. The design of GCLISP is such that it allows one GCLISP program to be used as data for another GCLISP program and hence the declarative and procedural knowledge can be easily executed. This feature is very useful for designing explanation facilities in expert systems. GCLISP allows defining procedures for carrying out numeric manipulations and evaluation of expressions. It requires very few declarations of data or data types, as do languages such as PASCAL.

3.1 Some important functions in GCLISP are presented in the following sections.

Atoms and Lists : Atoms are the basic indivisible objects in GCLISP. Here are some atoms: 3.14, ABC, X., BLOCK-A, 12, G-12, etc. Atoms are of two types: numbers, like 3.14, 12 etc, and symbols, ABC, X, Block-A, G-12, etc. A hyphen is treated just like any other character. Atoms are assembled together by GCLISP programmers to make larger objects. These larger objects are called LISTS. To mark the beginning and end of a list, a GCLISP programmer uses left and right parenthesis. Thus the lists may be: (THIS IS A LIST), (ABC LMN XYZ), (+ 1 2 3). Each piece of a list is called an element of the list. In the list (+ 1 2 3) the first element is the symbol +, the second is the number 1, etc. In GCLISP, The symbol that orders the object to execute some functions is called the PROCEDURE NAME. Whenever a list is used to specify computation, a procedure name is always the first element of the list. The rest of the elements in the list are the objects to work on. The objects to work on are called the ARGUMENTS. Hence, in the list (+ 1 2 3) the first element is the procedure name and the rest of the elements are arguments. A predicted is a procedure that trader returns either T or NIL. T is GCLISPese for true, NIL is GCLISPese for false. NOT makes T into NIL and visa-versa.

GCLISP has several tests that test to see what their arguments are:

Type of Predicate	Name of Test	Purpose
1. Equality predicate	1.1 Equal	Are two arguments the same?
2. Data type predicate	2.1 Atom	Is it an atom?
	2.2 Symbolp	Is it a symbol?
	2.3 Listp	Is it a list?
3. The list predicates	3.1 Endp	Is the argument an empty list?
	3.2 Member	Is a particular object is an element of the list.
4. The numeric predicates	4.1 Numberp	Is it a number?
	4.2 Zerop	Is it zero?
	4.3 Plusp	Is it positive?
	4.4 Minusp	Is it negative?
	4.5 =	Are they all equal?
	4.6 >	Are they in descending order?
	4.7 <	Are they in ascending order?

In many situations, it is natural to combine the results of two more predicates into a combined test. This is done by using AND or OR. AND returns to NIL if the evaluated value of any of its arguments are NIL. OR returns to NIL if the evaluated value of all of its arguments are NIL. Both AND and OR evaluate their arguments from left to right.

To put the list together, remained use primitives' card, called constructors are used

Name of Construct	Purpose
CONS	Add an element to an existing list.
LIST	Make a new list.
APPEND	combine two or more lists into one.
make a list in the reverse order from an existing one.	
purpose	
FIRST	Return first element of the list.
REST	Return list after removing the first element.
Return list after removing all but the last elements.	
Returns the number of elements in a list.	

Purpose

Evaluates all forms left to right, and returns the value of the first.

Evaluates all forms left to right, and returns the value of the second.

Evaluates all forms left to right, and returns the value of the last.

Conditional Primitives These are used when the value required depends on the result of some test. The simplest conditional primitives are WHEN and UNLESS. WHEN returns the value of the second argument when value of the first argument is anything other than NIL. In other words, WHEN triggers on non NIL. Here is the template:

(When<trigger><value if trigger non NIL>)

Similarly, UNLESS returns the value of the second argument when the value of the first argument is NIL. Said in another way, UNLESS trigger on NIL. Here is the template:(UNLESS <trigger><value if trigger NIL>)IF returns the value of the second argument when the value of the first argument is T or anything other than NIL; otherwise, it returns the value of the third argument. The template is as follows:(IF <trigger><value if trigger non NIL><value if trigger NIL>)These Conditional primitives are extensively used in this research work to develop rules; using these Functions the antecedent and consequent part of a rule can be developed. The antecedent part of a rule is the first argument of WHEN, UNLESS or IF. The consequent part of a rule is the second argument of WHEN and UNLESS and second or third argument of IF. Making little procedures GCLISP encourages creating small, easily debugged, procedures. LISP's procedure creating primitive a DEFUN is as follows :(DEFUN <Procedure name> (<Parameter>) <Form>) READ-Read something and return it without evaluating

3.2 Printing Using FORMAT

For elegance in printing, nothing beats FORMAT. Experts with FORMAT are considered talented artists. The general form for FORMAT is as follows (FORMAT <a specification of where to print > <a charter string with directives > < any number of additional arguments >)as an example, the printing using format assuming the value of L as (AA BB CC) is as follows: (Format t "~%The list ~A has ~D element ~P.") resulting in The list (AA BB CC) has 3 elements.

Components of expert systems

The expert systems developed in the present research work have user Interface, knowledge base, inference engine, working memory and Knowledge acquisition facility as their components in addition to it working memory of GCLISP facilitates the programmer great flexibility and power. Data structures are created dynamically without need for the programmer to explicitly allocate memory. Whenever uncertainty factors arises then the infection factor being handled using certainty factors developed as MYCIN project at Stanford University. In the present GCLISP also the uncertainty factors were handled by the same as the above method.

A Certainty Factor (CF [h, e]) is defined in terms of two Components, in the form $CF [h, e] = MB [h, e]$.

Where MB [h, e] a measure (between 0 and 1) of belief in a hypothesis 'h' given the evidence 'e', MB measure the extent to which the evidence supports the hypothesis, it is zero if the evidence does not support the hypothesis at all.

MD [h, e] a measure (between 0 and 1) of disbelief in a hypothesis 'h' given the evidence 'e', MD measures the extent to which the evidence supports the negations of the hypothesis, it is zero if the evidence supports the hypothesis. In the above factor CF corresponding to each rule is provided by the experts w If uncertain inferences are chained together, then the result should be less certain than either of the inferences alone. Having accepted the desirability of these properties, the several, pieces of evidence are combined to determine the CF of a hypothesis. The measure of belief and disbelief of a hypothesis given two observations s1 and s2 are computed using MYCIN combination, formula.

$$MB [h, s1\wedge s2] = 0, \text{ if } MD [h, s1\wedge s2] = 1 \\ = MB [h, s1] + MB [h, s2] (1 - MB [h, s1]) \dots \text{otherwise}$$

$$MD [h, s1\wedge s2] = 0, \text{ if } MB [h, s1\wedge s2] = 1 \\ = MD [h, s1] + MD [h, s2] (1 - MD [h, s1]) \dots \text{otherwise. One way to state these}$$

Formulae is that the measure of belief in h is 0 if h is disbelieved with certainty. In the present work, the uncertainties are handled exactly in the same manner as explained above with the necessary modification to suit the requirements of the problems. MB and MD in a problem, start with the value between 0 and 1, depending on the initial condition satisfied. The values of MB and MD continuously increase with the inclusion of subsequent observations. The expert system also takes into account vague and ambiguous information of factors and allows the user to express it as a percentage close to the corresponding ideal condition. The measure of belief and disbelief of evidence is being represented in the consequent part of the rule using sequence functions of GCLISP. These several pieces of evidence are combined in the consequent part of the rules using MYCIN combination formula, as explained above, to evaluate MB and MD and hence CF. A GCLISP program consists of several functions, which together with other statements work as a unit to perform the desired task. One can write the function definitions using a text editor or a structure editor. In GCLISP there is a structure editor, GMAC. Using 'LOAD' function of GCLISP, the programs are loaded. The entire interaction between the user and an expert system, and also the results can be stored in a separate file using 'DRIBBLE' function of GCLISP, and the print out of the same can be obtained later. The programs are developed in such a way that the system should recommend the first element of the list as first choice of the problem under consideration.

Development of GCLISP based AI the logic for this was developed after lengthy consultations with the experts in the field of irrigation and hydraulic structures. By combining their knowledge base, which is based in their vast experience in the field and the known facts in the conceptual process of selecting the type(s) of bridge foundation, an expert system, selection of best type(s) of bridge foundation was developed.

The use of the GCLISP based on the below guidelines, they are The friendly user interface is planned and developed in such a way that during interaction with the user, the expert system collects the data it needs to create and use as database. During interaction, the system displays questions to the user regarding the information it needs. There are different types of question scenarios in the expert system depending upon the nature of the information to be collected. The question answer scenario is provided with 'help' facility to guide the user to about how to respond to the queries. The help may be activated, and displayed automatically during user interaction or by demand or as a result of wrong respond by the user for a query. When the user demands, the expert system developed explains why a particular question is being asked.

Then input is in the form of friendly interaction with the users, the system interacts with the user for queries regarding information about topography, geological conditions, availability of materials and funds etc. in the interaction, the system displays questions to the user with necessary help and explanations to answer each query correctly.

The response of the user is specific such as either Y for yes, or N for no with facility of help. In the case of wrong response, the system repeatedly corrects the user, and repeats the question. This question-answer session is being developed as follows:

```
(prog ()
10
(prog ()
20
(prog ()
30
(format t "~%Is the magnitude of scouring large at the proposed site?~%")
(format t "~%
```

```
    PRESS Y-for yes,
        PRESS N-for no,
        PRESS P-for partial,
        Press H-for HELP.~%")
```

```
(setf s(read))
(when (numberp s)(progn
(format t "~%Your Response is wrong.It should be a symbol.~%"))(go 30)))
(when (equal s'h) (format t "~%When the velocity of the stream exceeds
the limiting velocity that can be withstood by the particles
of the bed material.~%")(go 20)))
```

```
(unless (progn (or (equal s'y)(equal s'ye)(equal s'yes)(equal s'n)
(equal s'no)(equal s'p))))
(progn(format t "~%Your Response is wrong.It should be Y/N/P.~%")(go 10))))
(setf k 0)
(prog ()
40
(prog ()
50
(when (equal s'p)
(format t "~%How much percentage it is close to large scour.~%")
(setf k(read))
(unless (numberp k)
(format t "~%Your Response is wrong. It should be a number.~%")(go 50))))
(when (progn(or(< k 0>(> k 100)))
(format t "~%
Your response is wrong.
It should be in between 0 and 100.~%")(go 40)))
```

In the above interaction regarding information about scour at the proposed site, the correct response is one of the four, viz, Y, N and P. The wrong response in the form of symbols other than mentioned above and all types symbols and numbers such as 12, 4, X, PP, YN, etc, the system guides the user with a message. Your “Your Response is wrong. It should be a symbol”. In case if user enters a number and “Response is wrong. It should be Y/N/P”, this statement displays if user gives symbols other than mentioned above, and repeats the question scenario on the screen. On pressing H, the system provides help to user as “When the velocity of the stream exceeds the limiting velocity that can be withstood by the particles of the bed material”. The correct response to this question is either Y or N or P. when the response is either Y or N, the system skips the second part of the question. However, on the other hand, when the response is P representing all intermediate condition between Y and N, the system allows the user to express the response as percentage of Y. The response should be always in between 0 and 100, otherwise the system is made to repeat the second part of this question with a warning. The correct response for first part is stored in the variable name ‘s’, or for second part the variable name is ‘k’.The system successfully completes the interaction for all the inbuilt standard factors generally considered in the selection of best type of bridge foundation at the proposed site.

The rider for the above software usage is, before running the above software ,a detail input is to be given in terms of collection of irrigation , land ,environmental data by interacting with the competent authorities and also inputs from geologist, geotechnical engineers and design engineers m A set of rules to assign the value of MB3 and MD3 of a well foundation is as follows: If scour, length, under ground water table, depth, hard strata are YES and perennial is NO then 0.2 should assigned to wfb1, wfb2, wfb3, wfb4, wfb5 and wfb6 respectively and if the scour is expressed in terms of percentage then it is assigned to wfb7. Similarly if scour, length, under ground water table, depth, hard strata are NO and perennial is YES then 0.2 should assigned to wfd1, wfd2, wfd3, wfd4, wfd5 and wfd6 respectively.

```
(prog ()
(setf xx 0)
(setf wfb1 0)
(setf wfb2 0)
(setf wfb3 0)
(setf wfb4 0)
(setf wfb5 0)
(setf wfb6 0)
(setf MB3 0)

(if(equal s'y)(setf wfb1 0.2))
(if(equal l'y)(setf wfb2 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 wfb2) wfb1) wfb2))

(if(or(equal g'n)(equal g'y))(setf wfb3 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) wfb3) xx))

(if(equal d'y)(setf wfb4 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) wfb4) xx))

(if(equal m'y)(setf wfb5 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) wfb5) xx))

(if(equal p'n)(setf wfb6 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) wfb6) xx))

(if(numberp k)(setf wfb7 (/ k 100)))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) wfb7) xx))
;(format t "~%MB3=~d~%" xx)

(setf wfd1 0)
(setf wfd2 0)
```

```
(setf wfd3 0)
(setf wfd4 0)
(setf wfd5 0)
(setf wfd6 0)
(setf MD3 0)
```

```
(if(equal s'n)(setf wfd1 0.2))
(if(equal l'n)(setf wfd2 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 wfd1) wfd2) wfd1))
```

```
(if(equal d'n)(setf wfd3 0.2))
```

```
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) wfd4) yy))
```

```
(if(equal m'n)(setf wfd4 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) wfd5) yy))
```

```
(if(equal p'y)(setf wfd5 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) wfd6) yy))
;(format t "~%MD3=~d~%" yy)
```

```
(setf CF3 (- xx yy))
(format t "~%CF3=~d~%" CF3))
```

A set of rules to assign the value of MB4 and MD4 of a pile foundation is as follows: If scour, length, under ground water table, depth, are YES and perennial, hard strata are NO then 0.2 should assigned to pfb1, pfb2, pfb3, pfb4, pfb5 and pfb6 respectively and if the scour is expressed in terms of percentage then it is assigned to pfb7. Similarly if scour, length, under ground water table, depth, are NO and perennial, hard strata are YES then 0.2 should assigned to pfd1, pfd2, pfd3, pfd4, pfd5 and pfd6 respectively.

```
(prog ()
(setf xx 0)
(setf pfb1 0)
(setf pfb2 0)
(setf pfb3 0)
(setf pfb4 0)
(setf pfb5 0)
(setf pfb6 0)
(setf MB4 0)
```

```
(if(equal s'y)(setf pfb1 0.2))
(if(equal l'y)(setf pfb2 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 pfb2) pfb1) pfb2))
```

```
(if(or(equal g'n)(equal g'y))(setf pfb3 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) pfb3) xx))
```

```
(if(equal d'y)(setf pfb4 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) pfb4) xx))
```

```
(if(equal m'n)(setf pfb5 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) pfb5) xx))
```

```
(if(equal p'n)(setf pfb6 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) pfb6) xx))
```

```
(if(numberp k)(setf pfb7 (/ k 100)))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) pfb7) xx))
;(format t "~%MB4=~d~%" xx)
```

```
(setf pfd1 0)
(setf pfd2 0)
(setf pfd3 0)
(setf pfd4 0)
(setf pfd5 0)
(setf pfd6 0)
(setf MD4 0)
```

```
(if(equal s'n)(setf pfd1 0.2))
(if(equal l'n)(setf pfd2 0.2))
```

```
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 pfd1) pfd2) pfd1))
```

```
(if(equal d'n)(setf pfd3 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) pfd4) yy))
```

```
(if(equal m'y)(setf pfd4 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) pfd5) yy))
```

```
(if(equal p'y)(setf pfd5 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) pfd6) yy))
;(format t "~%MD4=~d~%" yy)
```

```
(setf CF4 (- xx yy))
(format t "~%CF4=~d~%" CF4))
```

A set of rules to assign the value of MB5 and MD5 of a caisson foundation is as follows: If scour, length, under ground water table, depth, perennial, hard strata are YES then 0.2 should assigned to cfb1, cfb2, cfb3, cfb4, cfb5 and cfb6 respectively and if the scour is expressed in terms of percentage then it is assigned to cfb7. Similarly if scour, length, under ground water table, depth, perennial, hard strata are NO then 0.2 should assigned to cfd1, cfd2, cfd3, cfd4, cfd5 and cfd6 respectively.

```
(prog ()
(setf xx 0)
(setf cfb1 0)
(setf cfb2 0)
(setf cfb3 0)
(setf cfb4 0)
(setf cfb5 0)
(setf cfb6 0)
(setf MB5 0)
(if(equal s'y)(setf cfb1 0.2))
(if(equal l'y)(setf cfb2 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 cfb1) cfb2) cfb1))

(if(or(equal g'n)(equal g'y))(setf cfb3 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) cfb3) xx))
```

```
(if(equal d'y)(setf cfb4 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) cfb4) xx))
(if(equal m'y)(setf cfb5 0.2))
(setf x (+ (*(- 1 xx) cfb5) xx))
(if(equal p'y)(setf cfb6 0.2))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) cfb6) xx))
(if(numberp k)(setf cfb7 (/ k 100)))
(setf xx (+ (*(- 1 xx) cfb7) xx))
;(format t "~%MB5=~d~%" xx)
(setf cfd1 0)
(setf cfd2 0)
(setf cfd3 0)
(setf cfd4 0)
(setf cfd5 0)
(setf cfd6 0)
(setf MD5 0)
(if(equal s'n)(setf cfd1 0.2))
(if(equal l'n)(setf cfd2 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 cfd1) cfd2) cfd1))
(if(equal d'n)(setf cfd3 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) cfd4) yy))
(if(equal m'n)(setf cfd4 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) cfd5) yy))
(if(equal p'n)(setf cfd5 0.2))
(setf yy (+ (*(- 1 yy) cfd6) yy))
;(format t "~%MD5=~d~%" yy)
(setf CF5 (- xx yy))
(format t "~%CF5=~d~%" CF5))
```

After successful evaluation of measures of belief and disbelief of all the bridge foundation types, which qualify using data in the working memory, the certainty factors (CF) for all the bridge foundation types are calculated using the equation

$$CF = MB - MD$$

As soon as the system completes the evaluation of measures of belief and disbelief for all the factors, it creates the list of bridge foundation type(s) in the descending order of CF value. In a very rare situation two or more bridge foundation type(s) may acquire same CF value and emerge as first choice of bridge foundation type at the proposed site.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above experimental analysis following conclusions were drawn, they are as follows, The basic architecture of the expert system is mainly composed of user interface, knowledge base, inference engine, and knowledge acquisition facility and working memory. All these components are developed to suit the overall present as well as future requirements to select the best type(s) of bridge foundation at a proposed site. The uncertainty in the expert system is handled using Stanford model of certainty factors.

1. The input is in the form of friendly interaction with the user. It helps and guides the user how to enter the different types of input data.
2. The knowledge in the knowledge base is represented using production rules.
3. The inference engine which matches input data and knowledge in the knowledge base works on the principle of forward chaining.
4. The uncertainties are handled using Stanford model of certainty factor.
5. The system displays the choice of the foundation(s) in the order of merit.
6. It also displays the list of foundation(s) which cannot be adopted.

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NOTATIONS

AI=Artificial Intellegence

CF= certainty factors

MB=Belief (input parameter is correct)

MD=Disbelief(input parameter is not correct)

MYCIN=one of the competent authority developed one program on this aspect and this program MYCIN becomes input for developing our own program

GCLISP=Golden Common LISP is a popular and AI Language